

Leadership Practices of School Heads: Basis for Leadership Program for Intermediate Managers

Jessyl D. Cruz

Abstract. The study aimed to determine the level of the Leadership Program for Intermediate Managers and addressed sub-problems concerning Humility, Confidence, Empathy, and Open Communication. It was conducted in Santa Cruz South District, Division of Davao del Sur, with 16 school heads participating as respondents for the questionnaire. A universal sampling procedure was employed due to the small number of school heads in the district. Results indicated that school heads exhibited strong leadership practices, providing a foundation for designing effective leadership programs. The study revealed that these leaders incorporate techniques aimed at developing leadership skills among intermediate managers. Strong leadership among school heads is crucial for fostering resilient, high-performing schools capable of meeting the diverse needs of students and communities.

KEY WORDS

1. Leadership 2. Practices 3. School Head 4. Intermediate 5. Managers

Date Received: May 21, 2024 — Date Reviewed: May 23, 2024 — Date Published: June 5, 2024

1. Introduction

Leadership practices encompass a broad range of skills and behaviors that effective leaders employ to inspire and guide their teams towards achieving common goals. These practices are often studied and analyzed in various fields such as business management, psychology, and organizational behavior. One of the most influential frameworks on leadership practices is the "Five Practices of Exemplary Leadership" model developed by James Kouzes and Barry Posner. Leaders encourage innovation and growth by challenging the status quo, experimenting with new ideas, and taking calculated risks. They seek opportunities for improvement and encourage others to explore new possibilities. Leaders foster collaboration and build trust by empowering others to take initiative and contribute to the success of the team. They create an environment where individuals feel supported, valued, and capable of making meaningful contributions. These practices serve as a roadmap for leaders to develop and enhance their leadership skills, build strong relationships with their teams, and drive organizational success. Numerous studies and real-world applications have validated the effectiveness of these practices in various contexts, making them foundational principles in leadership development (Posner 2018). Leadership practices play a crucial role in organizational success, influencing everything from employee engagement to overall performance. Leadership practices that encourage innovation and adaptability are essential for staying competitive in today's rapidly changing business

landscape. A report by Deloitte emphasizes the role of leadership in fostering innovation and driving organizational agility. Leaders shape the culture of an organization through their actions and decisions. A study published in the *Journal of Leadership Organizational Studies* suggests that leadership practices significantly influence organizational culture, affecting factors such as communication, collaboration, and performance (Lange 2021). Leadership practices can create a supportive work environment where employees feel valued and appreciated, leading to higher job satisfaction and lower turnover rates (Judge 2018). Leadership practices that prioritize work-life balance, emotional support, and personal development contribute to improved employee well-being (Rhenen 2020). The impact of leadership practices on organizations and individuals is a widely studied subject in management and organizational behavior literature. Leadership practices significantly influence employee motivation and engagement levels. Transformational leadership, in particular, has been found to positively impact motivation and engagement (Bass, 1985; Avolio et al., 2019). Effective leadership practices are closely linked to organizational performance. Research indicates that leadership styles such as transformational and transactional leadership are associated with higher levels of organizational effectiveness (Piccolo 2020). Intermediate managers, also known as middle managers, occupy a crucial position within organizational hierarchies, serving as a bridge between senior management and frontline employees. They play a vital role in translating strategic goals into actionable plans and ensuring their implementation at the operational level. Intermediate managers are individuals within an organization who oversee teams or departments and are responsible for implementing organizational strategies, coordinating activities, and facilitating communication between senior management and frontline employees (Mintzberg 2021). Intermediate managers, often referred to as middle managers, play a crucial role in organizations by serving as a bridge between top management and frontline employees. Their importance lies in their ability to translate high-level strategic objectives into actionable plans and to facilitate communication and coordination across different levels of the organization. Intermediate managers often deal with conflicts and challenges that arise within

their teams or between different departments. Their ability to facilitate communication, negotiate solutions, and resolve conflicts is essential for maintaining organizational harmony and efficiency (Katz, 2019). Moreover, intermediate managers play a vital role in the functioning of organizations, acting as a linchpin between strategic objectives and operational execution.

1.1. Review of Related Literature—The literature below supports the existence of the problem under study, serving as a roadmap for the research. This review validates the study's significance.

1.1.1. Leadership Practices—Leadership practices involve behaviors and strategies by leaders to guide teams toward goals, emphasizing charisma, vision, and intellectual stimulation (Bass, 2022). Effective leadership shapes organizational culture and fosters a positive work environment (Schein, 2018), but unfair practices can undermine trust and morale (Greenberg, 2019).

1.1.2. Humility—Humble leaders acknowledge their limitations, admit mistakes, and recognize others' contributions. They seek feedback and prioritize collective good over personal ego, fostering inclusive and psychologically safe environments (Owens Hekman, 2020; Wong Davey, 2021). Humility in educational settings enhances school climate, teacher job satisfaction, and student achievement (Owens et al., 2022; Javidan et al., 2019).

1.1.3. Confidence—Confidence in educational leadership is essential for inspiring trust, fostering positive relationships, and driving improvement efforts. Confident leaders articulate compelling visions, make decisive decisions, and embrace innovation (Leithwood Jantzi, 2019). Distributed leadership, which shares responsibilities across stakeholders, fosters collective efficacy and confidence in addressing challenges (Spillane et al., 2018; Louis et al., 2020).

1.1.4. Empathy—Empathy in educational leadership is crucial for understanding the needs of students and faculty. Empathetic leaders build trust and rapport, improving communication and fostering a supportive school culture (Johnson Smith, 2020; Shriberg et al., 2018). Empathy enhances morale and productivity, promoting collaboration and teamwork (Borba, 2018; Dorothy, 2020). However, it can also lead to burnout if not managed effectively (Worline Dutton, 2019).

1.1.5. Open Communication—Open communication is vital for fostering trust and transparency among school stakeholders, facilitating problem-solving and decision-making, and encouraging innovation (Hong Lucas, 2020; Kolb Holzman, 2019; Tschannen-Moran Tschannen-Moran, 2021). It cultivates a positive school culture and increases engagement and commitment to the school's mission (Day et al., 2019; Louis et al., 2021).

1.2. Synthesis—The above-stated review of significant literatures discussed the prevalence of the problem under study in different context. They also discussed methodologies on how the current issue is solved. There are findings and recommendations presented to resolve the problem. These literatures backed up the occurrence of the problem and different localities present solutions. They also serve as roadmap to guide the researcher in the conduct of the study.

1.3. Theoretical Conceptual Framework—This study is anchored on the One widely cited theory of leadership practices is the Transformational Leadership Theory, proposed by James MacGregor Burns in his book "Leadership" (1978). This theory suggests that effective leaders inspire and motivate their followers by stimulating intellectual curiosity, promoting creativity, and fostering individual growth. Transformational leaders are known for their ability to create a vision, communicate it effectively, and empower their team members to achieve it. An-

Fig. 1. Schematic Diagram Showing the Flow of the Study.

other significant theory is the Situational Leadership Theory, developed by Paul Hersey and Kenneth Blanchard in the late 1960s. This model proposes that effective leadership depends on the readiness level of the followers. Leaders should adapt their leadership style based on the followers’ readiness, which encompasses their willingness and ability to accomplish a task. This is supported by a prominent theory concerning leadership programs is the Authentic Leadership Development (ALD) theory, proposed by Bill George (2003), former CEO of Medtronic and author of “Authentic Leadership: Rediscovering the Secrets to Creating Lasting Value,” ALD emphasizes self-awareness, transparency, and values-driven leadership. According to this theory, effective leadership develop-

ment programs should focus on helping individuals discover and embrace their authentic selves as leaders. This involves understanding one’s core values, strengths, weaknesses, and life experiences that shape their leadership style. ALD posits that authentic leaders are more resilient, inspiring, and capable of building trust and commitment within their teams and organizations. The diagram below illustrates the flow of the study. This study follows the input, process, output method where the input of the study is the Leadership Practice with the following indicators: Humility, Confidence, Empathy, Open Communication. The process used is through survey and the expected output is the Leadership Program for Intermediate Managers.

1.4. Statement of the Problem—This study seeks to determine the level of Leadership Pro-

gram for Intermediate Managers. Moreover, it seeks to answer the following sub-problems:

- (1) What is the level of Leadership Program for Intermediate Managers in terms of:
 - (1) Humility
 - (2) Confidence
 - (3) Empathy
 - (4) Open Communication
- (2) Base on the findings drawn out from the study, Leadership Program for Intermediate Managers can be proposed and designed?

1.5. Null Hypothesis—Since this study does not looked for significant relationship nor significant difference, this study is hypothesis

free.

1.6. Significance of the Study—The results and findings of this study will be beneficial to

the following: DEpEd. The Department of Education should know the results and findings of this study in order for them to create a policy that would consider online teaching as an integral modality to assist modular instruction in schools. Besides, the department will conduct a reorientation for all school leaders on the mechanics on the conduct of change management skills as basis for the Leadership Program for Intermediate Managers. School Heads. Being the manager in school, the school head needs to know the results and findings of this study for them to initiate school-based program that

would strengthen the Leadership Program for Intermediate Managers Teachers. The teachers should have extended extra miles by conducting online classes to make follow up on the lessons given to learners in the modules. Learners can be guided further if teachers give further instruction on the activity they are going to do that are found in the module. Future Researchers. The results and findings of this study will give insights to future researchers to the importance of Leadership Practices as an advantage on the part of the learners.

2. Methodology

This chapter presents the method of researched used, the researched design, researched subject, the research instruments, the data gathering procedure as well as the statistical treatment.

2.1. Research Design—This studied would made used of a descriptive-co-relation non-experimental quantitative researched method. It is descriptive because the data are presented in quantitative descriptions on the “Leadership Practices of School Heads”. According to Gay (2006) descriptive-correlation design determines and supports the way things were. Used a questionnaire in conducting a surveyed, interview or observations usually

collects the data.

2.2. Research Respondents—The study has been conducted in Santa Cruz South District, Division of Davao del Sur. The respondents of this study will be the 16 school heads of the research locale to answer the questionnaire. Universal sampling procedure will be utilized in this study in determining the respondents considering the small number of school heads of Santa Cruz South District.

2.3. Research Instrument—In this study, one (1) set of questionnaires will be used. It is a researcher-made questionnaire which will be validated by experts of the study and will be subjected later to a reliability test using cronbach alpha. It will be pilot tested to a school that

is not a part of the research locale. The questionnaire focuses on the items of Leadership Practices of School Heads through checklist. To determine the level of Leadership Practices of School Heads, the following continuum will be used:

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—The steps involved in this investigation are as follows:

A letter seeking for permission that this research study be conducted will be sent to the DepED superintendent of Davao del Sur, SDS

Nelson C. Lopez, CESO VI and to the School Principals concerned. While letters seeking for permission were delivered to the schools division superintendent and principals concerned, the researcher constructed a questionnaire and have it validated by the experts and eventually

Distribution of Respondents

School	Number of School Heads
Santa Cruz Central ES	1
Patulangon ES	1
Loay Elementary School	1
Agripina Elementary School	1
Tuban Elementary School	1
Ciriaco Gudoy Elementary School	1
Anastancio G. Canda Elementary School	1
Tagabuli Elementary School	1
Sinuron Elementary School	1
Melilla Elementary School	1
Saliducon Elementary School	1
Matutungan Elementary School	1
Apolinar Franco Elementary School	1
Total	13

Range of Means	Level	Description
4.30 – 5.00	Very High	When the change Leadership Practices of the newly hired school heads is manifested all the time.
3.30 – 4.29	High	When the Leadership Practices of School Heads is frequently manifested.
2.30 – 3.29	Fair	When the Leadership Practices of School Heads is sometimes manifested.
1.30 – 2.29	Low	When the Leadership Practices of School Heads is rarely manifested.
0 – 1.29	Very Low	When the Leadership Practices of School Heads is never manifested.

subjected it to reliability test using cron bach alpha. After permission has been granted that this study be conducted in Santa Cruz South District, Division of Davao del Sur and after the research questionnaire has been thoroughly examined by the expert validators, the researchers will launch the questionnaire into the field and

retrieved them from the respondents personally after few days. The data generated from the survey will be collated and tallied personally by the researcher. The raw scores will be submitted to the statistician for statistical computation after which the researcher subjected it to analysis and interpretation.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—

Fig. 2. Certificate of Appearance Tuban Elementary School

Fig. 3. Certificate of Appearance Patulangon Elementary School

Fig. 4. Certificate of Appearance Agripina Elementary School

Task	Jan 2023	Feb 2023	Mar 2023	April 2023	May 2023	Aug 2023	Sept 2023	Oct 2023	Jul 2024
Title Defense	█								
Outline Defense		█							
Validation of Questionnaire		█							
Conduct of the Study			█						
Retrieval of Questionnaire				█					
Interpretation and Analysis					█				
Final Defense						█			
Incorporation of Comments and Suggestions							█		
Seeking the signature of Panel Members								█	
Graduation Day									█

Fig. 5. Gantt Chart

The following statistical tools will be used: Average Weighted Mean will be used to determine the level of Leadership Practices of School Heads

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the discussion of the problems in this study. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Level of Leadership practices of newly hired school heads in terms of Humility, Confidence, Empathy and Open Communication.

3.1. Level of Leadership Practices of School Heads in terms of Humility—Table 1 shows the level of lesson reinforcement skills in terms of lesson drill. In this discussion the following responses yielded by the respondents are given for a comprehensive emphasis: Acknowledges mistakes with a rating of 4.38 or very high, Treats everyone with courtesy and respect with a rating of 4.10 or high, Cares about the feelings and experiences of others with a rating of 4.36 or very high, Understand own weaknesses and strengths with a rating of 4.07 or high, and Appreciates blessings and oppor-

tunities in their life with a rating of 4.35 or very high. It got an overall mean rating of 4.25 or high. This means that school heads often-times manifest leadership practices in terms of humility. Owens Hekman (2020) provides evidence for this viewpoint. Humility in leadership within educational settings is an increasingly recognized and valued trait. Humble leaders in schools demonstrate a willingness to seek and accept feedback from various stakeholders, including teachers, students, parents, and administrators. They view feedback as an opportunity for growth and improvement rather than as a threat to their authority.

Humility in leadership refers to a leader’s willingness to acknowledge their own limitations, admit mistakes, and recognize the contributions of others. Humble leaders are open to feedback, receptive to diverse perspectives,

and prioritize the collective good over personal ego. They create an inclusive and psychologically safe environment where employees feel valued, respected, and empowered to contribute their best. Act organizational culture, employee

Table 1. Level of leadership Practices of School Heads in terms of Humility

	Mean	Description
a. Acknowledges mistakes	4.38	Very High
b. Treats everyone with courtesy and respect	4.10	High
c. Cares about the feelings and experiences of others	4.36	Very High
d. Understand own weaknesses and strengths	4.07	High
e. Appreciates blessings and opportunities in their life	4.35	Very High
Overall	4.25	High

engagement, and overall performance (Mitchell, 2018). Humble leaders foster a collaborative and inclusive environment where all members of the school community feel valued and respected. They actively involve stakeholders in decision-making processes and recognize the contributions of every individual towards achieving common goals (Owens et al., 2019). Humble leaders practice transparency in their actions and decisions, openly sharing information and communicating their intentions with honesty and integrity. They hold themselves and others accountable for their actions and demonstrate a commitment to ethical conduct (Kaplan et al., 2020).

3.2. *Level of Leadership Practices of School Heads in terms of Confidence*—Table 2 presents the level of leadership practices of school heads in terms of confidence. In this discussion the following responses yielded by the respondents are given for a comprehensive emphasis: Gets happiness from within with a rating of 4.20 or high, Speaks with certainty with a rating of 4.15 or high, Listens more than speaks something with a rating of 4.05 or high, Doesn't seek attention of others with a rating

of 4.25 or very high, and Celebrates the victory of others with a rating of 4.10 or high. It got an overall mean rating of 4.15 or high. This means that school heads oftentimes manifest leadership practices in terms of confidence. This is congruent to the idea of Jantzi (2019) who cited that confident educational leaders are more adept at articulating a compelling vision for the school and setting clear goals aligned with educational priorities. Confident leaders are more decisive and effective in making difficult decisions, such as resource allocation, curriculum development, and personnel management. Confidence enhances leaders' communication skills, enabling them to effectively communicate with stakeholders, inspire others, and foster a sense of shared purpose and commitment. This is supported by Leithwood and Jantzi (2019) who highlighted the importance of confidence in leadership practices in schools. They found that principals who exhibited high levels of confidence in their leadership abilities were more likely to create a positive school climate, promote teacher collaboration, and facilitate student achievement.

3.3. *Level of Leadership Practices of School Heads in terms of Empathy*—Table 3 emphasizes the level of leadership practices of

school heads in terms of empathy. In this discussion the following responses yielded by the respondents are given for a comprehensive em-

Table 2. Level Leadership Practices of School Heads in terms of Confidence

	Mean	Description
a. Gets happiness from within	4.20	High
b. Speaks with certainty	4.15	High
c. Listens more than speaks something	4.05	High
d. Doesn't seek attention of others	4.25	High
e. Celebrates the victory of others	4.10	High
Overall	4.15	High

phasis: Sees things from another perspective with a rating of 4.40 or very high, Feels emotion of other persons with a rating of 4.26 or high, Reduces other persons distress as well as your own with a rating of 4.33 or very high, Listens to people without interrupting with a rating of 4.00 or high, and Understands people even if you don't agree with them with a rating of 4.06 or high. It got an overall mean rating of 4.21 or high. This means that school heads oftentimes manifest leadership practices in terms of empathy. This concept aligns with Shriberg, et al.

(2018) notion that empathy plays a crucial role in effective leadership, particularly in educational settings where school heads serve as key figures in shaping the school environment and fostering positive relationships among students, staff, and parents. Empathetic leaders demonstrate an understanding of the thoughts, feelings, and perspectives of others. By listening actively and showing empathy, school heads can build trust and rapport with students, teachers, and parents, creating a supportive and inclusive school community.

Table 3. Level Leadership Practices of School Heads in terms of Empathy

	Mean	Description
a. Sees things from another perspective	4.40	Very High
b. Feels emotion of other persons	4.26	High
c. Reduces other persons distress as well as your own	4.33	Very High
d. Listens to people without interrupting	4.00	High
e. Understands people even if you don't agree with them	4.06	High
Overall	4.21	High

Johnson and Smith (2020) provide support for this. They emphasize the significance of empathy in educational leadership, particularly among school heads. They argue that effective leaders in educational settings demonstrate high levels of empathy, allowing them to connect with students, teachers, and other stakeholders

on a deeper level. This empathetic approach fosters trust, collaboration, and a positive school climate, ultimately leading to improved academic outcomes and overall school success." Educational leaders who demonstrate empathy create a supportive and nurturing environment where individuals feel understood, respected,

and valued. By acknowledging and validating the emotions of others, school heads can support the emotional well-being of students, teachers, and parents, contributing to a positive school culture (Dorothy, 2020).

3.4. *Level of Leadership Practices of School Heads in terms of Open Communication*—Table 4 emphasizes the level of leadership practices of school heads in terms of open. In this discussion the following responses yielded by the respondents are given for a comprehensive emphasis: Conveys thoughts freely with a rating of 4.29 or high, Communicates feelings, challenges confidently with a rating of 4.38 or very high, Values every workers unique perspective with a rating of 4.41 or very high, Encourages constructive and positive feedback

with a rating of 4.22 or high, and Expresses ideas to one another with a rating of 4:11 or high. It got an overall mean rating of 4.28 or high. This means that school heads often-times manifest leadership practices in terms of open communication. This concept aligns with Day, Kington, Stobart, Sammons (2019) notion that open communication is integral to effective leadership practices in schools. It builds trust, enhances problem-solving capabilities, and encourages innovation, ultimately contributing to the overall success and well-being of the school community. Open communication cultivates trust among all members of the school community, leading to increased engagement and commitment to the school’s mission and goals.

Table 4. Level Leadership Practices of School Heads in terms of Open Communication

	Mean	Description
a. Conveys thoughts freely	4.29	High
b. Communicates feelings, challenges confidently	4.38	Very High
c. Values every worker’s unique perspective	4.41	Very High
d. Encourages constructive and positive feedback	4.22	High
e. Expresses ideas to one another	4.11	High
Overall	4.28	High

Trust Matters: Leadership for Successful Schools (2021) provide support for this. open communication encourages innovation and continuous improvement. When teachers, administrators, and other stakeholders feel comfortable sharing their ideas and suggestions, it creates an environment conducive to experimentation and growth. Research by Megan Tschannen-Moran and Sharon L. Tschannen-Moran emphasizes

this point, demonstrating that open communication promotes innovation in educational settings. Open communication contributes to the development of a positive school culture characterized by mutual respect, support, and a sense of belonging, which fosters a conducive learning environment for students (Louis, Dretzke, Wahlstrom, 2021).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter displays the summary of the findings, conclusions and recommendations drawn out by the researcher after the analysis and interpretation of the findings had been made. This

study seeks to determine the level of the leadership practices of school heads which will be the basis in designing a leadership program for intermediate managers. This study employed the non-experimental descriptive survey research design in investigating the research problem. It is descriptive because the data are presented in quantitative descriptions on the “Leadership Practices of School Heads: Basis for Leadership Program for Intermediate Managers”. According to Good (2005), this method of research shows merely description of tasks presenting the conditions regarding the nature of the group of persons or class of events that involved procedure of analysis, classification, and measurement. It involves varied information regarding the current or present condition (Deauna, 2005). This study will be conducted in Sta Cruz South District. The respondents in this study are the 16 school heads of the research locale. The respondents’ leadership practices will be assessed through researcher-made questionnaire. The researcher will write a letter to the school heads concern so that the above-mentioned data will be given to her. This study revealed that school heads possess good leadership practices that would serve as a basis in designing leadership program. It is revealed in this study that school heads embed in the leadership practices some techniques that would develop leadership skills for intermediate managers. Strong leadership practices for school heads is essential for building resilient, high-performing schools that can meet the diverse needs of their students and communities.

4.1. Conclusions—Based on the collective findings on this study, the following conclusions are drawn: The level of leadership practices of school heads in terms of Humility is High, Confidence is High, Empathy is High, and the Open Communication is High.

4.2. Recommendations—In the light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations are offered: The Department of Education Officials should impose that would consider online teaching as an integral modality to assist modular instruction in schools. Besides, the department should conduct a reorientation for all school leaders on the mechanics on the conduct of change management skills as basis for the Lead-

ership Program for Intermediate Managers. The school heads should initiate school-based program that would strengthen the Leadership Program for Intermediate Managers. In addition, school heads should conduct periodic evaluations of the leadership program to assess its effectiveness and make necessary adjustments. Use surveys, feedback sessions, and performance metrics for comprehensive assessment. Teachers should conduct regular workshops and seminars with educational leaders and subject matter experts to provide practical insights and interactive learning experiences. For future researchers, it is encouraged that they will conduct similar study on leadership development of intermediate managers in another setting and another time.

5. References

- Avolio, B. J., & Yammarino, F. J. (Eds.). (2019). *Transformational and charismatic leadership: The road ahead*. Emerald Group Publishing.
- Bass, B. M. (1985). *Leadership and performance beyond expectations*. Free Press.
- Bono, J. E., & Judge, T. A. (2018). Self-concordance at work: Toward understanding the motivational effects of transformational leaders. *Academy of Management Journal*, 46(5), 554–571.
- Borba, M. (2018). *Unselfie: Why empathetic kids succeed in our all-about-me world*. Touchstone.

- Bryk, A. S., & Schneider, B. L. (2018). *Trust in schools: A core resource for improvement*. Russell Sage Foundation.
- Chancellor, J., & Lyubomirsky, S. (2019). Humble beginnings: Current trends, state perspectives, and hallmarks of humility. In J. A. D. Lennick & R. W. Kiel (Eds.), *Moral intelligence 2.0: Enhancing business performance and leadership success in turbulent times* (pp. 185–210). Pearson.
- Dixon, A. L. (2018). The relationship between principals' emotional intelligence and leadership practices. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 45(6), 987–1005.
- Dorothy, E. (2020). *Empathy in leadership: A guide to leading with emotional intelligence*. Routledge.
- Gallup. (2019). State of the american workplace report.
- Greenberg, J. (2019). A taxonomy of organizational justice theories. *Academy of Management Review*, 12(1), 9–22.
- Javidan, M., Dorfman, P. W., Sully de Luque, M., & House, R. J. (2019). In the eye of the beholder: Cross cultural lessons in leadership from project globe. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 30(1), 67–89.
- Jennings, P. A., & Greenberg, M. T. (2020). The prosocial classroom: Teacher social and emotional competence in relation to student and classroom outcomes. *Review of Educational Research*, 79(1), 491–525.
- Johnson, S., & Smith, L. (2020). The role of empathy in educational leadership: A review of current literature. *Educational Leadership Review*.
- Judge, T. A., & Piccolo, R. F. (2020). Transformational and transactional leadership: A meta-analytic test of their relative validity. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 89(5), 755–768.
- Kaplan, S., Cortina, J., Ruark, G., & LaPort, K. (2020). The role of organizational humility in organizational learning. *Organization Science*, 25(4), 1210–1227.
- Katz, D. (2019). The motivational basis of organizational behavior. *Behavioral Science*, 19(2), 85–115.
- Kouzes, J. M., & Posner, B. Z. (2018). *The leadership challenge: How to make extraordinary things happen in organizations*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Louis, K. S., Dretzke, B., & Wahlstrom, K. (2021). How does leadership affect student achievement? results from a national us survey. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 21(3), 315–336.
- Louis, K. S., Leithwood, K., Wahlstrom, K. L., & Anderson, S. E. (2010). *Investigating the links to improved student learning: Final report of research findings*. University of Minnesota.
- Marzano, R. J., Waters, T., & McNulty, B. A. (2018). *School leadership that works: From research to results*. ASCD.
- Mintzberg, H. (2021). *The nature of managerial work*. Harper & Row.
- Owens, B. P., & Hekman, D. R. (2020). Modeling how to grow: An inductive examination of humble leader behaviors, contingencies, and outcomes. *Academy of Management Journal*, 55(4), 787–818.
- Owens, B. P., Johnson, M. D., & Mitchell, T. R. (2018). Expressed humility in organizations: Implications for performance, teams, and leadership. *Organization Science*, 24(5), 1517–1538.

- Peterson, S. J., Galvin, B. M., & Lange, D. (2021). Ceo servant leadership: Exploring executive characteristics and firm performance. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*, 19(2), 154–164.
- Rothschild, J., & Lamm, J. (2020). *The power of emotionally intelligent leadership: Leading with emotional courage*. Pearson.
- Schaufeli, W. B., Bakker, A. B., & Van Rhenen, W. (2020). How changes in job demands and resources predict burnout, work engagement, and sickness absenteeism. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 30(7), 893–917.
- Schein, E. H. (2018). *Organizational culture and leadership* (4th). Jossey-Bass.
- Sergiovanni, T. J. (2021). *Rethinking leadership: A collection of articles: The principled principal: How you can help your school improve*. Rowman & Littlefield Education.
- Shriberg, A., Shriberg, D. L., & Kumari, A. (2018a). *Practicing leadership principles and applications*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Shriberg, A., Shriberg, D. L., & Kumari, A. (2018b). *Practicing leadership principles and applications*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Souto-Manning, M. (2019). *Feminist teacher activism: Claims, change, and everyday acts*. Teachers College Press.
- Spillane, J. P., Halverson, R., & Diamond, J. B. (2018). Towards a theory of leadership practice: A distributed perspective. *Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 36(1), 3–34.
- Wong, P. T. P., & Davey, D. (2021). Best practices in promoting leadership character development. In R. J. Burke, C. L. Cooper, & C. Antoniou (Eds.), *The human resources revolution: Why putting people first matters* (pp. 269–293). Elsevier.
- Worline, M. C., & Dutton, J. E. (2019). *Awakening compassion at work: The quiet power that elevates people and organizations*. Berrett-Koehler Publishers.